

Factors Affecting Mathematics Teachers' Espoused Beliefs towards Teaching

Mathematics

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Abstract

This study represents the part of the data collected for the PhD completion of the researcher. The aim of this paper was to investigate the affecting factors of mathematics teachers' espoused beliefs towards teaching mathematics. Focused Group Discussion was used to gather the information from eight groups of mathematics teachers of Chitwan, Makawanpur, Gorkha and Parsa districts and two groups of Head teachers of Chitwan district. The constant comparison analysis method of qualitative research was used for conducting the research. The result showed that the teacher education program, training of teachers, philosophical and curriculum related factors and satisfaction of teachers influenced mathematics teachers' espoused beliefs.

Keywords: espoused beliefs, under pinning factors, enacted beliefs, secondary leveled teachers,

Introduction

Ernest, (1991) has revealed that different plans prepared by the mathematics teachers and the activities based on the plans affect the teaching learning process of mathematics. He has further explained that the plans and activities of mathematics teachers' have been affected by their beliefs about nature of mathematics and teaching learning process of mathematics. So, the performances of mathematics teachers depend on their beliefs. Teachers' beliefs are the parts of understanding of the teachers which shape the different types of activities performed by them in the classroom teaching. Teachers' belief systems represent their personal values, norms and theories about the nature of knowledge which ultimately influence the application of curriculum in classroom and different teaching methods process and approaches (Pajares, 1992). He has further elaborated that each mathematics teacher has beliefs related to mathematics, mathematics teaching and other mathematics teaching activities known as espoused beliefs. Espoused beliefs are based on their experiences as a student and as a teacher. It is also based on philosophy of education, knowledge level and teacher education program.

Different researches (Shilling, 2010; Goldin, 2002; Törner, 2002; Kyungsoon, 2000; Kramer, Randy, McDuffie & Tad, 1998;

Raymond, 1997; Calderhead, 1996; Orton, 1996; Pehkonen, Torner & Leder, 2003; Richardson, 1996; Pajares, 1992; Ernest, 1988; Nespor, 1987; Hersh, 1986; Kuhs & Ball, 1986 as cited in Thompson, 1992; Thompson, 1984; Lerman, 1983; Green,

1971) related to teachers' beliefs and students learning identify the underpinning factors for construction of teachers' beliefs but these researches have been indifferent about the factors like job satisfaction, schooling of teachers, motivational factors, society and culture of teachers as well as available sources. These researches have been unable to categorize the factors clearly which are responsible for the development of teachers' espoused beliefs. So, categorization of factors affecting teachers' espoused beliefs is one of the emerging issues in the field of mathematics education.

Research Methodology

The constant comparative method of qualitative research was used for the systematic finding of the study. The study was based on the secondary level mathematics teachers of Chitwan, Gorkha, Makawanpur and Parsa districts. Non-probability sampling method is more suitable than the probability sampling procedure when the research is conducted on qualitative approaches (Gupta, 2005; Best & Kahn, 2006; Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2010). This study has focused on issues related to mathematics teachers' espoused beliefs. The purposive sampling method is suitable to identify solution of certain issues and fulfill the purposes of the study (Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2010; Gupta, 2005). So, two groups of mathematics teachers from

mathematics teachers from Makawanpur district, two groups of mathematics from Gorkha district, and two groups of mathematics from Parsa district were selected by using purposive sampling method representing the rural and urban areas of these districts. Thus, these eight groups of mathematics teachers were considered as the sample for underpinning factors of teachers' espoused beliefs. The convenience sampling method is the best method for selecting sample from the population among the different methods of non-probability sampling when the researcher wants to take the information from easy way and to obtain the supplement information of the qualitative study (Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2010; Gupta, 2005). So, two groups of Head Teachers/Principals from Chitwan district were selected by using convenience sampling procedure. So, these two groups of Head Teachers were also the sample for underpinning factors of teachers' espoused beliefs. Two focused group discussion were used for collecting the data from these eight groups of mathematics teachers and two groups of head teachers. Both FGD were prepared on different theories, the bases of teachers' responses on questionnaire and their actual classroom practices.

This study used the information collected from the FGD for eight groups of mathematics teachers and two groups of Head Teachers for finding out the underpinning factors of teachers' espoused beliefs. Triangulation procedure of validity is suitable for this research since this uses the information collected from multiple and different sources (Creswell & Miller, 2000). Triangulation combines the information obtained from different informants to highlight the main gist or theme of the research. Triangulation procedure of validity employs researcher's lens and systematic paradigm for categorizing the data (Creswell & Miller, 2000). External auditor is a person expert in subject matter of the study but he has no connection to the study (Creswell & Poth, 2018). External auditor examines both the process and the product of the study for assessing their accuracy. External auditor procedure of validity employs external to the study lens and systematic paradigm for categorizing the data (Creswell & Miller, 2000). The external auditor examines whether or not the findings, interpretations, and conclusions generated in the study are supported by the data. This process also provides a sense of inter-rater reliability to a study (Creswell & Poth, 2018). The reliability or dependability of any qualitative research can be established by using the procedures of triangulation and external auditor (Long & Johnson, 2000). Validity and reliability of any qualitative research must be established in the research process (Creswell & Poth, 2018; Creswell & Miller, 2000; Patton 2014; Long & Johnson, 2000). So, this research used triangulation and external auditor procedures for establishing validity and reliability in its qualitative aspect. The data obtained from the FGD were discussed with the two college level teachers having at least M. Phil. degree and two mathematics teachers having at least Master degree and 20 years of teaching experiences for external auditor of validating.

I have used the part of the data for this study collected for my PhD research. Teachers groups were formulated on the basis of responses on the questionnaire of the quantitative part of the

district were invited from those teachers whose mean marks on the traditional method of teaching mathematics is more than 3. The second group for Chitwan district were invited from those teachers whose mean marks on the traditional method of teaching mathematics is less than 3. The mean marks of the responses on the constructivist method of teaching mathematics of all teachers were more than 3. So, responses of the traditional method of teaching mathematics were taken as the basis for grouping. The same kinds of activities were done in Gorkha, Makawanpur and

Parsa districts. Ten participants were invited by using purposive sampling method for each group. Logistic supports were managed for the needy participants. Two groups of Head teachers consisting of 10 head teachers were invited from the sample school of Chitwan district by using convenience sampling method. The name of groups, name of districts, number of participants presented, FGD conducted time, and date were mentioned in following table.

The table 1 shows types of FGD conducted for this study. The first FGD is for teachers of eight groups representing two groups for each district. The FGD for teachers contains the questions based on the research questions. There are two main questions related to the first research question which represents the teachers' espoused beliefs, three main questions related to the second research question, three main questions related to the third research questions and three main questions related to the fourth research question of the qualitative aspect. The FGD for

Table 1
Participators present in focused group discussion

S. No.	The name of groups	Name of districts	FGD date	FGD time	Number of participants
1	CH T1	Chitwan	Sept, 1, 2018	10:00-11:30	8
2	CH T2	Chitwan	Sept, 1, 2018	3:00-4:30	7
3	GO T1	Gorkha	Sept, 29, 2018	11:00-12:30	6
4	GO T2	Gorkha	Sept, 29, 2018	11:00-12:30	6
5	MA T1	Makawanpur	Sept, 15, 2018	10:30-12:00	8
6	MA T2	Makawanpur	Sept, 15, 2018	2:00-3:30	9
7	PA T1	Parsa	Sept, 22, 2018	10:00-11:30	6
8	PA T2	Parsa	Sept, 22, 2018	2:00-4:30	7
9	CH H1	Chitwan	Sept, 8, 2018	10:00-11:30	6
10	CH H2	Chitwan	Sept, 8, 2018	3:00-4:30	8

questions of the study. There are two main questions related to the first research question, three main questions related to the

second research question, three main questions related to the third research questions and three main questions related to the fourth research question.

Data Analysis of the Study

The constant comparison analysis method of qualitative data analysis was used to investigate the affecting factors of the mathematics teachers' espoused beliefs which was originally developed by Glaser and Strauss (Glaser, 1992; Strauss, 1987). According to Leech and Onwuegbuzie (2008), there are seventeen methods of qualitative data analysis. Among them, constant comparison analysis method is one of the suitable methods for analyzing the qualitative data obtained from focused group discussion. Initially, this method was used for grounded theory. The credit goes to Leech and Onwuegbuzie (2007) for using this method in other types of data analysis including constant comparison analysis method. There are three phases (open coding, axial coding and selective coding) of constant comparison analysis. It uses the process of coding (open, axial, and selective) in data analysis and generates the theory with clear visual picture (Creswell, 2011). In first stage the data obtained from the qualitative study are divided into small units and they are attached with a code (Strauss & Corbin, 1998). Then the codes are categorized into different groups in the second stage (Strauss & Corbin; 1998). Finally in third stage, the researchers developed a theme or themes that represent the core ideas of each category (Strauss & Corbin; 1998). It focuses on development of theoretical categories from the collected data rather than using specific preset categories (Strauss & Corbin; 1998). Constant comparison analysis is suitable method of qualitative data analysis when there are multiple focus groups in the same research study and it helps the researchers to reach in the final point in the data analysis (Leech, Dickinson, Zoran & Onwuegbuzie; 2009). This study has focused on the underpinning factors of teachers' espoused beliefs and data were collected from the focused group discussion of eight groups of mathematics teachers and two groups of Head Teachers. So, constant comparison analysis is appropriate for this study.

First of all, I used the information collected from questionnaire and focused group discussion notes and formed the initial categories for different underpinning factors for teachers' espoused beliefs which is open coding (Creswell, 2011) for the data analysis. The sources (questionnaire, FGD, and my notes) of the information which support the categories of underpinning factors were clearly stated. Secondly, I used axial coding (Creswell, 2011) of open coding. For axial coding, the initial categories were re-categorized from the most influencing factors for teachers' espoused beliefs to the least influencing factors. I also compared these categories with different theories and philosophies of teachers' espoused beliefs. Thirdly, I used selective coding (Creswell, 2011). In this process, I explained the different abstract process which were used in research process and developed a theory from the interrelationship of the categories in the axial coding model.

teachers of Chitwan district said, “The thinking about teaching was influenced by his school's mathematics teacher” (FGD, CH T1). Most teachers’ agreed that their beliefs and thinking about mathematics teaching were germinated in their school life and mathematics teachers of their schools. “I have got the ideas of developing and using teaching materials from the B.Ed. program and I am using these ideas” (FGD, MA T5). The mathematics teachers of all districts expressed that their feeling and thinking about teaching method and using teaching materials were generated from the courses included in B.Ed. and M.Ed. program. One of the teachers from Gorkha district said, “My teaching techniques are based on the training on micro teaching program in B.Ed.” (FGD, GO T3). They said that they got ideas for developing different teaching materials, using them in appropriate time, using different method and techniques for different topics of mathematics from participating in the program. From this discussion, experiences of teachers from his school’s life and experience from learning teacher education program was one of the influencing factors of teachers’ espoused beliefs. Mathematics teachers shared their happiness for participating in peer teaching, discussion with peers and microteaching. All of them agreed that they had got a lot of things and their mental structure of mathematics teaching were reformed from the interaction and teaching in peers. According to them, they had got several techniques about teaching from peers and internal supervisor (College teacher) in micro teaching program. So, experiences of teachers in micro teaching of teacher education program was another affecting factors of teachers’ espoused beliefs. Teachers expressed that they experienced real situation of mathematics teaching from school teaching of B.Ed. program. They got guidelines and feedback from the subject teachers of the school, internal supervisor of the college and participating in different programs and activities of schools in the period of teaching practice. Thus, school teaching program of practice teaching was also affecting factors of mathematics teachers’ beliefs. The teacher education program of Nepal aims to develop the trained, committed and competent teachers for school level. These information reveal that the teacher education program has significant impact on teachers’ espoused beliefs. So, the teacher education program (experience of teachers in regular learning of teacher education program; experience of teachers in micro and peer teaching of teacher education program; and experiences of teachers from teaching practice of teacher education program) is the most affecting factor of mathematics teachers’ espoused beliefs.

“I have reformed and changed my teaching style based on the knowledge and skills obtained from the participation in different workshops, seminars, interaction programs and research training” (FGD, PA T7). Teachers mentioned that their attitudes towards teaching were shaped from the daily teaching experiences, academic teaching culture of school, ideas generated from teaching specific topics, sharing ideas among teachers in leisure time. One of the teachers from Gorkha district said, “Today teaching is becoming easier because we can use internet for everything” (FGD, GO T3). They confessed that demo class included in YouTube, reading different articles in internet and journals as well as different experiences obtained from society

and daily
life also
shaped
their

intention of teaching. From this discussion, teachers' espoused beliefs were also influenced by the experience and in-service training of teachers (training program, experiences of teachers from teaching and teachers' experiences other sources).

Mathematics teachers articulated that different methods, techniques and materials used in mathematics teaching were also reformed their view of teaching. They got ideas of new thing in mathematics teaching from these things and new innovation. In discussion program, mathematics teachers accepted that different philosophy of education, teachers' own religion and culture, their internal philosophy from life experiences and different learning theories also played the role in developing teachers' espoused beliefs. Most of the teachers expressed that government policy towards mathematics teachers and training program was not good. In one group of FGD, one of the teachers said, "If teacher education program is ineffective, it is government's duties to make it effective but government is in the way of using untrained teachers in mathematics teaching" (FGD, CH T1). S/he further explained, "Can government use non medicine graduate for the treatment of patient if some patient has lost his/her life by the treatment of MD doctor?" (FGD, CH T1). Mathematics teachers agreed that curriculum and its related factors, evaluation system of mathematics in secondary level, resources available to the teachers and national policy of mathematics and education also affected their views of mathematics and mathematics teaching. So, philosophical and curriculum related factors (religion and teachers' philosophy; learning theories; curriculum and its aspects; methods and techniques of mathematics teaching) was another underpinning factor of mathematics teachers' espoused beliefs.

Some teachers shared their bad feeling about the salary of secondary level teaching. "Our salary is very low as compared with the other professional employees salary and we have to do other part time job to fulfill our family needs" (FGD, PA T8). They expressed that they had to do other part time job to fulfill their personal needs. Status of satisfaction from teaching, incentive to the teachers, fulfillment of personal needs from teaching were taken as the influencing factors of teachers thinking about teaching mathematics based on the discussion of teachers. They said that the school administration had to provide equal opportunity to all the teachers otherwise the teacher who did not get any role in school's regular activities could develop the negative attitude towards teaching. They also expressed that students' achievement, their participation in learning and attitude towards teachers also affected mathematics teaching. So, satisfaction from profession (motivational factors and student related factors) was also affecting factors of mathematics teachers' espoused beliefs.

- i. Experience of teachers in regular learning of the teacher education program, experience of teachers in micro and peer teaching of the teacher education program and experiences of teachers from teaching practice of the teacher education program influenced the mathematics

he experience and in-service training of teachers like training program, experiences of teachers from teaching and teachers' experiences of other sources also affected mathematics teachers' espoused beliefs.

- iii. Philosophical and curriculum related factors like religion and philosophy of teachers, learning theories, curriculum and its aspects as well as method and techniques of mathematics teaching affected mathematics teachers' espoused beliefs.
- iv. Satisfaction from profession like motivational factors and student related factors affected mathematics teachers' espoused beliefs.

Discussion

The results from the discussion in this study inform that the teacher education program affects the teachers' espoused beliefs. Teacher development programs change the teachers' espoused beliefs (Bell & Gilbert, 1994; Clark and Peterson, 1986; Fennema and Franke, 1992; Mischo & Maab, 2013; Pajares, 1992, Perry et al., 2006; Raymond, 1997; Richards, Gallo and Renandya, 2002; Wilkin, 2008; Yu, 2008). The discussions with the mathematics teachers for this study reveal that the in-service training of teachers also changes the mathematics teachers' espoused beliefs. Previous studies related to mathematics teachers' beliefs also conclude that the teacher training program affects the teachers' espoused beliefs (Clark and Peterson, 1986; Joyce & Showers, 2002; Sang, Valcke, Braak & Tondeur, 2010). Mathematics teachers have common consensus about the philosophical and curriculum related factors that are the intervening factors of the secondary level mathematics teachers' espoused beliefs. The researchers in the field of mathematics education accept the philosophy of mathematics and mathematics education is one of the underpinning factors of mathematics teachers' espoused beliefs (Ernest, 1988; Hannula, Kaasila, Pehkonen & Laine, 2005; Pepin, 1999; Perry, 1970). All of the secondary level mathematics teachers participated in the discussion program agreed about the satisfaction from profession influence mathematics teachers' espoused beliefs. The researches related to mathematics teachers' beliefs were indifferent to the effect of the motivational factors in mathematics teachers' espoused beliefs. But, the motivational theories (Maslow, 2043; Alderfer, 1969; McClelland, 1987; Adams, 1963; Herzberg, 1959) inform that the motivational and satisfaction from the profession affect the thinking of employees about the profession. The teacher education program, the in-service training of teachers, the philosophical and curriculum related factors and the satisfaction from profession are main four factors which influenced the mathematics teachers' espoused beliefs.

Conclusion

The aim of this study is to identify the underpinning factors of the Nepalese mathematics teachers' espoused beliefs. The beliefs of the mathematics teachers are the thinking,

assumption about a mathematics and teaching learning process of mathematics which they think to be true. From the discussion, it is concluded that teacher education program, the experience and in-service training of teachers, philosophical and curriculum related factors and satisfaction from profession are main four factors which influenced the mathematics teachers' espoused beliefs about teaching learning process of mathematics.

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